

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 7.4

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network

Project Final Conference

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Disclaimer

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Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Union's Research Executive Agency with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project has contributed to addressing the multiple challenges that farming systems are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

The European Committee of the Regions hosted the joint final conference of the two EU-funded projects ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: Preparation phase and [AE4EU – Agroecology for Europe](#), the sister project of ALL-Ready, in Brussels on 27 September 2023. The one-day conference shed light on how the two projects paved the way for a European Network of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. Stories from the field and local stakeholders were featured by both projects, with an emphasis placed on the Pilot Network of ALL-Ready. Experiences from involved living labs and research infrastructures provided practical insights into the agroecology transition in Europe. The two projects decided to organize a joint conference in order to maximise outreach and impact, thanks to the complementarity of activities, project outcomes and network of stakeholders.

1.1 Purpose of the Deliverable

This deliverable aims at giving an overview of the ALL-Ready final conference including its outreach to policy-makers, funders as well as communities of living labs and research infrastructures.

2. Summary of the conference

2.1 Co-organisation and attendance

The one-day conference was held to consolidate and disseminate the results achieved by ALL-Ready and AE4EU and through the Pilot Network established by ALL-Ready. The collaboration of the two projects covered the development of the agenda (annex 1), as well as the selection and invitation of speakers and moderators, the venue and catering arrangements, and the facilitation of the conference. The follow-up work was primarily done by ALL-Ready.

Supporting materials from the two projects as well as from the involved living labs and research infrastructures were made available on the day of the conference. From the side of ALL-Ready, the project flyer, the policy briefs and a multilingual booklet were presented, offering a comprehensive introduction to the Pilot Network as a collective entity. This booklet served as an additional platform for the living and research infrastructures involved in ALL-Ready to exhibit their activities. It was translated into six languages and made accessible online, with download facilitated by QR codes displayed at the conference venue. Additionally, a limited number of printed copies were made available.

The conference was attended by 123 participants from 29 European and non-European countries (Annex 3), which ensured maximum impact and uptake of the projects' results by a wide range of stakeholders, including funders and policy makers.

2.2 Main messages

At the EU level, both the European Commission and the Committee of the Regions recognise the pivotal role that agroecology can play in supporting key policies such as the Green Deal. Roberto Berutti, a Member of the Cabinet for Agriculture Commissioner Janusz Wojciechowski and a keynote speaker at the conference, highlighted the significance of living labs in not only achieving but surpassing environmental, climate, farming, and biodiversity policy objectives.

Agroecology has a strong regional dimension because there is no one-size-fits-all approach to agroecological practices. Heinz-Joachim Höfer, from the European Committee of the Regions, emphasised the pivotal role of regions in enhancing agricultural sustainability and resilience, highlighting the necessity of regulatory changes and increased agricultural knowledge for this transition.

Agroecology requires adaptive management and collaboration among scientists, practitioners, policy-makers, and consumers, therefore living labs and research infrastructures are at the core of facilitating agroecology transition. Heather McKhann (INRAE), coordinator of the ALL-Ready project, highlighted the importance of diversity in establishing resilient systems and achieving ultimate success. This diversity encompasses various actors, including land and infrastructure owners, communities, authorities and researchers, who should collaborate in a transdisciplinary manner. Moreover, diversity extends to biodiversity, farming systems, and the composition of living labs and other open innovation networks.

"The upcoming European partnership on agroecology is an excellent step in the right direction, but undoubtedly it will only be a start. Long term political and financial investment is needed to make the necessary changes." Heather Mckhann

Insights from living labs and research infrastructures in several European countries have highlighted the significance of sharing know-how and best practices. These experiences have revealed a diverse range of local activities, including seed swaps, local farmers' markets, soil health workshops, the establishment of alternative food systems, and engagement with farmers across various stages, from participatory research to policymaking.

Participants in the final panel reached a consensus that adequate funding and other forms of assistance are needed at local, regional, and national levels to support sustainable agri-food systems.

Both ALL-Ready and AE4EU play a significant role in shaping the AGROECOLOGY Partnership – Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures, to be launched in early 2024 under Horizon Europe. This partnership aims to accelerate the transition to agroecology across Europe by supporting a network of living labs and research infrastructures.

Nicolas Tinois, the coordinator of the partnership, emphasised the overarching mission of the partnership, which is to achieve significant scientific, social, and economic impact through an approach involving both short-term and long-term objectives.

After the conference, a [press release](#) was distributed to over 500 recipients, including conference participants, as well as additional researchers and policymakers. The recording of the conference is available on the two project websites.

3. Acknowledgements

This report is compiled for the Horizon 2020 ALL-Ready project (Grant Agreement No. 101000349). We would like to thank the initiatives and funding organisations for participating in the interviews and workshops and for their valuable input to the discussion of the added value of a European Network for Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures reported in this deliverable.

Hyperlink: www.all-ready-project.eu

More information

Recordings of the conference: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/communication/news-events/news/recordings-of-the-final-conference.html>

Press release of the conference: <https://www.all-ready-project.eu/communication/news-events/news/how-living-labs-and-research-infrastructures-can-support-the-agroecology-transition-in-europe-insights-from-two-european-projects-all-ready-and-ae4eu.html>

European Partnership: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/agriculture-forestry-and-rural-areas/ecological-approaches-and-organic-farming/partnership-agroecology_en

Annex 1 - Programme of the conference

Final agenda - Morning session

- 08:30-09:00 Welcome coffee
- 09:00-09:10 Opening of the conference
Christian Huyghe, Scientific Directorate of Agriculture, French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE) (facilitator of the morning session)
- 09:10-09:25 Welcome from the European Committee of the Regions
Heinz-Joachim Höfer, Commission for Natural Resources, European Committee of the Regions
- 09:25-09:50 Keynote: Change from the ground up: systemic transition towards agroecology
Roberto Berutti, Cabinet of Commissioner for Agriculture Janusz Wojciechowski, European Commission
- 09:50-10:15 A short history and outlook of the European partnership AGROECOLOGY
Nicolas Tinois, AGROECOLOGY partnership, Project Management Jülich (Ptj)
- 10:15-10:45 Coffee break & marketplace
- 10:45-11:00 Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures - the European context
Kerstin Rosenow, Unit Research & Innovation, DG AGRI, European Commission
- 11:00-12:00 Experiences from ALL-Ready - Vision, mission, and implementation of a (pilot) network of agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures, Q&A
Torsten Rødel Berg, ALL-Ready project, Department of Agroecology, Aarhus University (AU)
Chris McPhee, ALL-Ready project, Living Labs Division, Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC)
Gerald Schwarz, ALL-Ready project, Thünen Institute of Farm Economics
Korinna Varga, ALL-Ready project, Agricultural Policy Group, Hungarian Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (ÖMKI)
Heather McKhann, ALL-Ready project, French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE) (moderator)
- 12:00-12:30 Experiences from AE4EU - Mapping Agroecology and Living Labs in Europe
Baptiste Grard, AE4EU project, Isara France
Alexander Wezel, AE4EU project, Isara France
- 12:30-13:45 Lunch & marketplace

ALL-Ready and AE4EU have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements no 101000349 and 101000478.

Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures in Europe

Experience from ALL-Ready and AE4EU

27 September 2023 - European Committee of the Regions, Brussels

Final agenda - Afternoon session

- 13:45-14:45 Panel: How can Living Labs and Research Infrastructures support the agroecology transition? Q&A
Martina Desole, European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)
Jan Hassink, Wageningen Research
Chris McPhee, Living Laboratories Division, Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC)
Lavanya Premvardhan, European Research Infrastructure Consortium on Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems (AnaEE-ERIC)
Paola Migliorini, University of Gastronomic Sciences (UNISG) Polenzo (moderator)
- 14:45-16:15 Practice perspectives: How to put agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures in practice? Q&A
Rebecca Swinn, Soil Association (United Kingdom)
Iria Soto, E-Science European Infrastructure For Biodiversity And Ecosystem Research (LifeWatch-ERIC) (Spain)
Véronique Bellon-Maurel, Occitanium Living Lab (France)
Bregje Hamelynck, Federation of Agroecological Farmers (Netherlands)
Giuliana Radosta, Agroecological Living Lab Val Varaita (Italy)
Judith Conroy, Coventry University (United Kingdom)
Sylvie Foselle, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO) (moderator)
- 16:15-16:45 Coffee break & marketplace
- 16:45-17:45 Panel: How can regions best support agroecology, Living Labs and Research Infrastructures? Q&A
Gunilla Andersson, Department for Environmental Management, City of Malmö
Francesca Ricardi di Netro, Free University of Bozen-Bolzano
Gerald Schwarz, Thünen Institute of Farm Economics
Bénédicte Blaudeau, Pays de la Loire Europe
Susana Saez Gaona, Unit Research & Innovation, DG AGRI, European Commission (moderator)
- 17:45-18:00 Concluding remarks
Heather McKhann, ALL-Ready project, French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE)
Alexander Wezel, AE4EU project, Isara France
- 18:00-19:30 Networking reception

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Annex 2 - Pictures

Figure 1. Opening of the conference by Heinz-Joachim Höfer, representative of the Commission for Natural resources, European Committee of the Regions (Source: FiBL, Lisa Haller)

Figure 2. Panel discussion on how to put agroecology living labs and research infrastructures in practice. Moderator: Sylvie Foselle, ILVO. (Source: FiBL, Lisa Haller).

Annex 3 – List of participants

The list of the participants is provided below.

Only the participants who have given their consent to be included in the participant list for networking purposes are listed here (121 out of the 123 participants).

N.	Last name	First name	Organisation	Country
1	Aertsens	Joris	Flanders Government - Department of Agriculture	Belgium
2	Agboton	Martin	AgriCord	Benin
3	Ambühl	Elena	Agroecology Europe	France
4	Andersson	Gunilla	City of Malmö	Sweden
5	Angarita	Erika	Thuenen Institute	Colombia
6	Avila	Jose Manuel	LifeWatch ERIC	Spain
7	Bellon	Stéphane	Inrae	France
8	Bellon Maurel	Veronique	INRAE	France
9	Bender	Johannes	Federal Office for Agriculture and Food	Germany
10	Berg	Torsten Rødel	Agroecology, Aarhus University	Denmark
11	Bernard Mongin	Claire	UMR Innovation - Cirad	France
12	Berutti	Roberto	European Commission	n/a (EC)
13	Bieliauskaite	Simona	Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Lithuania	Lithuania
14	Bijttebier	Jo	ILVO Flanders	Belgium
15	Bingol	Bige Olcay	ECVC- European Coordination Via Campesina	Turkish Republic
16	Blaudeau	Bénédicte	Pays de la Loire Europe	France
17	Bonnet	Ophélie	INRAE	France
18	Bozsogi	Boglarka	Agroecology Europe	Hungary
19	Brendel	Louis	INRAE	France
20	Bretagnolle	Vincent	CNRS CEBC	France
21	Bruere	Cécile	INRAE OccitANum	France

22	Butler Manning	David	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	Ireland
23	Cala Rodriguez	Miguel Angel	FiBL Europe	Spain
24	Canali	Stefano	CREA-AA	Italy
25	Capurro	Federico	European Commission	Italy
26	Cavallo	Dolinda	ENoLL	Italy
27	Chandel	Rajeshwar Singh	University of Horticulture and Forestry, Nauni, Solan India	India
28	Chauhan	Sanjeev	University of Horticulture and Forestry, Nauni, Solan India	India
29	Christensen	Henriette	AEEU	Denmark
30	Climent	Juan	AEI	Spain
31	Conroy	Judith	Coventry University	UK
32	Couture	Isabelle	European Network of Living Labs	Canada
33	Csonka	Valéria	ÖMKI	Hungary
34	Dauby	Vincent	Agroecology Europe	Belgium
35	De Cock	Lieve	ILVO-LLAEBIO	Belgium
36	De Meerleer	Anja	Government	Belgium
37	de Morteuil	Emilie	The House of Agroecology	Belgium
38	De Schampelaere	Kristine	PAN Europe	Belgium
39	Delalieux	Stephanie	VITO	Belgium
40	Er	Cumhur	Brussels Municipality	Belgium
41	Feher	Judit	FiBL Europe	Hungary
42	Fievez	G. Francis	Consortium C4S consulting	Belgium
43	Fleck	Mami	Mitsui & Co. Deutschland GmbH	Japan
44	Fosselle	Sylvie	ILVO	Belgium
45	Gaba	Sabrina	INRAE	France
46	Gabrielli	Monica	Laimburg Research Centre	Italy

47	Galiana	Cristina	CSIC-UPV Ingenio Institute	Spain
48	Gaona Saez	Susana	European Commission	n/a (EC)
49	Gernert	Maria	IFOAM Organics Europe/TP Organics	Germany
50	Giatsidou	Vasiliki	ELGO-DIMITRA (GREECE)	Greece
51	Girardin	Cyril	INRAE	France
52	Goldel	Bastian	University of Pisa	Germany
53	Grard	Baptiste	Isara	France
54	Haller	Lisa	FiBL Europe	Austria
55	Hamelynck	Bregje	Federation of Agro-ecological Farmers/CSA Network Netherlands	Netherlands
56	Hassink	Jan	Wageningen Research	Netherlands
57	Hellström	Sara	Thünen Institute	Sweden
58	Hochner	Daniel	Hochner	France
59	Hrenova	Jana	Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic	Slovakia
60	Huyghe	Christian	Inrae, France	France
61	Ibrahim	Heba	Forschungszentrum Jülich	Egypt
62	Jacquet	Florence	ANR	France
63	Kamilia	Kintan	ISARA - AE4EU	Indonesia
64	Kovacs	Eszter	Project Springboard	Hungary
65	Landuyt	Carmen	CCBT	Belgium
66	Le Toquin	Esther	Ver de Terre Production	France
67	Lerin	François	AIDA	France
68	Loconto	Allison	INRAE	Italy
69	Lopez	Daniel	Spanish National Research Council	Spain
70	Malfroid	Cedric	Skynet	Belgium
71	Mambrini Doudet	Muriel	IRD	France

72	Manevski	Kiril	Aarhus University	North Macedonia
73	Marchand	Fleur	ILVO	Belgium
74	Matt	Mireille	INRAE	France
75	Maurissen	Diane	C-BASC of Université Paris-Saclay VivAgriLab)	Belgium
76	McKhann	Heather	INRAE	France
77	Mieves	Esther	Vereinigung Ökologischer Landbau in Hessen e.V.	Germany
78	Migliorini	Paola	University of Gastronomic Science	Italy
79	Mimmo	Tanja	Free University of Bolzano	Italy
80	Moeskops	Bram	FiBL Europe	Belgium
81	Montelone	Daniel	ELO	Italy
82	Montignies	Eddy	BRIOAA	Belgium
83	Moraut	Helene	European Committee of the Regions	France
84	Muraru	Constantin	European Agroforestry Federation	Romania
85	Novak	Sandra	INRAE	France
86	Oehen	Bernadette	FiBL	Switzerland
87	Palomino Antolin	Irene	Fundecyt-PCTEX	Spain
88	Papadopoulos	Philip	INOFA	Greece
89	Peskovicova	Dana	NPPC - National Agricultural and Food Centre	Slovakia
90	Pieruschka	Roland	EMPHASIS / Forschungszentrum Jülich	Germany
91	Premvardhan	Lavanya	AnaEE-ERIC	India
92	Radosta	Giuliana	Living Lab Valle Varaita	Italy
93	Ramos	María	CICYTEX	Spain
94	Ricardi di Netro	Franceca	Free university of Bozen - Bolzano	Italy
95	Riedel	Antonia	Ecologic Institute	Germany
96	Sacchi	Giovanna	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	Italy

97	Sanchez	Benjamin	AEI - Spanish Funding Agency for Research	Spain
98	Sanchez Blanco	Manuel	FECYT, FSP	Spain
99	Savary	Clara	INRAE	France
100	Saverys	Simon P.	DIGNITY SERVICE	Belgium
101	Schmutz	Ulrich	Coventry University, Centre for Agroecology, Ryton Organic Gardens	UK
102	Schwarz	Gerald	Thünen Institute of Farm Economics	Germany
103	Soto Embodas	Iria	LifeWatch ERIC	Spain
104	Stas	Arnaud	SPW/Cellule Intégration Agriculture Environnement	Belgium
105	Stojacic	Isidora	BioSense Institute	Serbia
106	Studnitz	Merete	ICROFS/AU	Denmark
107	Thiele	Jan	Thünen Institute	Germany
108	Thilini	Fernando	University of Coventry	Sri Lanka
109	Tinois	Nicolas	JÜLICH	Germany
110	Traup	Lukas	NABU	Germany
111	Triantafyllidi	Ioanna	Wageningen University	Greece
112	Trkulja	Ivana	International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems, Aarhus University (AU-ICROFS)	Italy
113	Ulmer	Karin	Independent Consultant	German
114	Van Nieuwenhove	Tom	Inagro	Belgium
115	Varga	Korinna	ÖMKi	Hungary
116	Volcic	Valerija	Plant ETP	Slovenia
117	Walter	Dietmar	BMBF	Germany
118	Wezel	Alexander	ISARA	Germany
119	Wustenberghs	Hilde	ILVO	Belgium
120	Zanotelli	Damiano	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	Italy
121	Ziegler	Ulrike	Juelich	Germany

